

TYPES OF LEDGERS IN S4 HANA FINANCE

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3 types of ledgers

Leading Ledger

Non Leading Ledger

Extention Ledger

Standard Extension Ledger

Simulation Ledger

Prediction Ledger

IMPORTANT POINTS ON EACH LEDGER

Leading Ledger

- Only one ledger can be defined in SAP, and it is assigned to all the company codes by default
- All transactions will be recorded
- Takes over properties (fiscal year variant, posting period variant, and first currency) from the company code
- Data will be stored in respective tables like ACDOCA, BSEG

Non Leading Ledger

- Based on Accounting principle wise will create non leading ledger
- we can maintain different currency, fiscal year and posting period
- Physically data stores in standard tables like ACDOCA, BSEG
- Non Leading Ledger are activated by company code
- We can maintain separate document number range in non leading ledgers

Extension Ledger

- Underlying ledger is Leading/ Non Leading ledger
- Extension ledger specific postings updated in ACDOCA
- It will inherit certain characteristics from its parent ledger (ex. Fiscal year, currency)
- Posting period can be different
- Extension ledger cannot be integrated with Controlling & Asset Accounting
- The extension ledger won't consume the database, it derives data from the Standard ledger
- Extension ledgers no need to assign to company code

Simulation Ledger

- This will use only for Foreign currency valuation
- Base or underlying ledger is Leading/Non leading ledger
- Data stores in ACDOCA and FAGL_BSBW_HISTSM
- In update run data delete from above tables
- Line items with technical names with deletion possible

Predictive Ledgers

- Used to update statistical condition values at the time of billing
- Underlying ledger is leading/non leading ledger
- Update in ACDOCA table only with prediction ledger
- Line items with technical names with non deletion possible

Ledger:	Non-leading ledger (compared to leading ledger)	Extension ledger (compared to leading ledger)
• Different currency settings possible?	Yes	No
• Different fiscal year variant (FYV) possible?	Yes	No
• Different posting period variant possible?	Yes	Yes
• Different accounting principle possible?	Yes	Yes
• Different company code assignment possible?	Yes	Yes

Scenario:

Streak BS headquarter at USA has subsidiaries in India (company code 2000) and Canada (company code 3000).

Both company code is required to produce financial reports using different accounting principle and in various currencies to Headquarter USA.

Below picture showing accounting books needed for Streak BS India .

As per Indian regulations fiscal year is 1st APR to 31 March

As per The fiscal year for the United States federal government runs from October 1 to September 30

Local GAAP in INR currency - Fiscal year for India is 1ST APR to 31st MAR

US GAAP in INR, USD - Fiscal year 1st OCT to 31st SEP

IFRS in INR, USD – Fiscal year 1ST APR to 31st MAR

If user post a document It will flow to all ledgers

If user post a document to specific ledger then it will be display only that particular ledger

User can post ledger specific postings through FB50L, FB01L, FV50L

Thank You